

Research Article

Potency of Na-Humate from Subbituminous and how to do Incubation with Fosfor-Fertilizer to Increase Upland Rice Production at Acidic Mineral Soil

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ABSTRACT

This research was purposed to study the ability of Na-humate from *subbituminous* combined with P-fertilizer and the way of incubation to control metals Al, soil fertility improvement and productivity of acidic minerals soil (Ultisol), so that the use of fertilizer could be saved and the optimal production of upland rice can be achieved. The experiment was designed using a 3 x 4 factorial with 3 replications in randomly groups design. The 1st factor was 3 ways of incubating Na-humate with P-fertilizer which are : I₁ = Incubation of Na-humate 1 week, then incubation P-fertilizer 1 week; I₂ = Incubation of Na-humate and P fertilizer directly into the soil for 2 weeks; and I₃ = Na-humate and P fertilizer mixed for 1 week, then incubation to the soil for 1 week. The 2nd factor was Na-humate and P-fertilizer combination which are 4 doses H₁ = 400 ppm (0.8 Mg/ha) + 100% R; H₂ = 400 ppm + 75% R; H₃ = 800 ppm (1.6 Mg/ha) + 100% R.; and H₄ = 800 ppm + 75% R. The results showed that the best treatment interaction was founded to be 800 ppm Na-humate and 100% R P-fertilizer doses in I₃ way incubation that is equal to 5.58 Mg/ha rice yield. However, this result is almost the same as 800 ppm Na-humate + 75% R P-fertilizer doses followed in I₃ way incubation too. It was concluded that addition of Na-humate could save P-fertilizer up to 25%.

Keywords:

Na-Humate, *Subbituminous*, P-Fertilizer, Upland Rice, Acidic mineral soil

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, agribusiness development can be done by utilizing marginal and sub-optimal land outside Java. Most of that land is dominated by acidic mineral soils such as Ultisol and Oxisol. Ultisol has around 45.79 million hectares or 24.3%, and Oxisol has around 14.11 million hectares or 7.5% of the total land area of Indonesia. These lands are distributed in Sumatra, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, and Papua (Pusat Penelitian dan Pengembangan Tanah dan Agroklimat, 2004). Its main problem of land to use for agricultural development is primarily heavy metal toxicity of aluminum (Al) and iron (Fe) as well as nutrient deficiencies, especially phosphorus (P) in plants. Elements of Al and Fe are highly dissolved in acid soils, it would be easy to bind P, so that it caused less responsive and low efficiency addition of P-fertilizer for plants (Hardjowigeno, 2003).

Solution for this problem usually can be done by adding organic matter (manure, green manure, and compost) to the soil, but it needs a long time process decomposition and reaction in soil. Using of Na-Humate as component of humic compounds have a rapid reaction, more active, electrical charge and a cation exchange capacity (CEC) that is greater than minerals clay. It can provide Na-humate extracted by 0.5 N or 0.1 N NaOH from *subbituminous* (low rank coal that unproductive) (Tan, 2003).

Stevenson (1994) Fiorentino *et al.*, (2006) and Tan (2010) stated that control of Al and Fe toxicity and increased availability of P by giving humic compounds may occur through the formation of chelate or organo-metallic complexes, so the activity of metal Al and Fe in soil can be reduced and non-toxic to plants. A direct usage of humic compounds into the soil stimulate plant growth, nutrient uptake and many other physiological processes, but when use indirectly, could improve soil fertility by altering the soil physical, chemical, and biological properties. Then the use of humic compounds can modify plant growth media, namely by improving soil structure, increase soil water holding capacity and soil CEC. Research on the extraction of Na-humate from *subbituminous* and its use for agriculture particularly in improving the efficiency of P-fertilizer and upland rice production are still rare in Indonesia, hence the need to investigate.

P-fertilizer application technology like incubation of P-fertilizer and organic matter before it is given into the soil for P efficiency can be done. Organic materials will accelerate solubility of P fertilizers. P-fertilizer is not contacting with the soil directly and quickly available, therefore fixation of P can be reduced. Murnita (1995) reported that incubating P fertilizer (TSP) and manure for 4 weeks before being given to the soil, so that the case could be increased fertilizer efficiency by 7.2% to 11.1% of the corn. Furthermore Herviyanti and Gusnidar (1999) reported that the application of fertilizer P (SP-36) that incubated first with manure for one week, before they were given into the land, could improved dry shelled corn grain yield of 3.24 Mg/ha to 3.81 Mg/ha. And then, it is needed to investigate incubated Na-humate from

subbituminous with P-fertilizer to obtain optimal results and how to use it.

This research is very necessary in order to study the ability of *subbituminous* combined with P-fertilizer and how to use them to control the metals Al, and improve soil fertility, increase the productivity of acidic mineral soil in the field, so that the use of fertilizer can be reduced and the optimal production of upland rice can be achieved.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research design

Subbituminous (Low-rank coal) was provided from Bonjol District, Pasaman Regency, and West Sumatra Province, Indonesia. *Subbituminous* was taken at a depth of 1-2 meters. finely milled using stone smoothing machine (grondong). Mixed 4 kg *Subbituminous* and 20 liters of 0.5 N NaOH (ratio 1: 5) (Modified method Tan, 1996), then both materials inserted into the tube of material subsequent grinding machine milled for 3 hours and then filtered, distillate is Na-humate. This material can be treated in the Ultisol soil types.

The experiment was conducted in farmers' land (Sari Lamak village, 50 Kota Regency, West Sumatra Province, Indonesia). The experiment was arranged in a 3 x 4 factorial experiment with 3 replications and placed in a randomized block design (RBD). As the first factor was 3 ways incubation Na-humate from *subbituminous* to fertilizer P are:

I₁ = Incubation of Na-humate 1 week, then 1 week of P-fertilizer incubation to the soil

I₂ = Incubation of Na-humate and fertilizer P in the soil for 2 weeks

I₃ = Na-humate and P fertilizers were mixed for 1 week, and then inserted into the soil and incubated for 1 week.

Factor II was a combination treatment of Na-humate and P fertilizers consisting of 4 levels. This combination has given a better response from the greenhouse experiments of research Herviyanti *et al.* (2009). The dose combination of Na-humate and P-fertilizer P is selected:

H1 = 400 ppm Na-humate (0.8 Mg/ha) and P-fertilizer 100% recommendation

H2 = 400 ppm Na-humate (0.8 Mg/ha) and 75% P fertilizer recommendation

H3 = 800 ppm Na-humate (1.6 Mg/ha) and fertilizer P 100% recommendation

H4 = 800 ppm Na-humate (1.6 Mg/ha) and 75% P fertilizer recommendation.

Recommendation (R) P-fertilizer used is 300 kg/ha SP-36, as a comparison was plot without Na-humate and P-fertilizer (control). Besides, to convince farmers also conducted fertilizing in accordance with the tradition of local farmers (100 % R P-fertilizer). Both treatments

were also done as many as 3 replications. The number of experimental plots are all (3 x 4 x 3) plots + (2 x 3) plots = 42 plots.

Experimental implementation

Tillage was done by digging the land to be planted, then made plots measuring 3 m x 2 m, a total of 42 squares. The distance between plots was 0.5 m and the distance between blocks 1 m. Soil sample was taken of 500 g on land prior to land treatment for chemical analysis of early land. Further Na-humate and P-fertilizer were incubated according to the number of the plot in experimental design and covered with plastic. After incubation is complete, soil sampling was done by \pm 500 g for the chemical analysis of the soil. The upland rice variety used was Inpage 6. Planting was done by planting 5 seeds per hole with a spacing of 25 cm x 25 cm (population = 77 plants per plot). Urea and KCl fertilizer given in accordance with their recommendations are 200 kg/ha Urea and 150 kg/ha KCl respectively. General plant maintenance includes watering, weeding, and controlling pests and plant diseases.

Plant sampling for analysis of Al and P contents were taken at the time of maximum vegetative growth that is at the age of 76 days after planting (DAP). The sample consists of the top (stem and leaves) and the bottom (root) plant by cutting the base of the stem at the root collar boundary. Harvest plants were conducted at 118 DAP. The grains were completely dried and then weighed.

Observation

Soil observations was carried out on the analysis of initial soil as a control and analysis of soil after incubation to include: analysis of pH H₂O (1: 1) with a pH meter method, available P with Bray II method, Al-dd with the volumetric method, and CEC by the method of leaching with 1 N ammonium acetate pH 7.

Plant observations were conducted on plant nutrient level, grain weight, and weight of 1000 seeds. To determine the dry weight of plants, the top and the roots were taken and put into perforated envelope, then inserted to an oven at a temperature of 60 ° C for 2 x 24 hours and weighed dry weight. The sample was milled with a grinder. Al and P content of plants were determined using wet methods of destruction. Grain samples were weighed (wet weight), then dried until the weight remains in the oven with a temperature of 60 ° C for 2 x 24 hours, and weighed again and the oven dry weight calculated seed weight moisture content (MC) 14%. Weight of 1000 seeds obtained by weighing 1000 grains were taken randomly from each treatment per plot that had been oven-dried at a temperature of 60 ° C for 2 x 24 hours. Then weighed dry weight of 1000 seeds.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil analysis results once given the combination of

Na-humate and P-fertilizer on some ways incubation.

pH and Al-dd of soil

The results from statistical analysis of the effect of Na-humate from combination with P-fertilizer in some ways incubation to pH and Al-dd of Ultisol are presented in Table 1. The effect interaction giving of Na-humate combination with P-fertilizer in several different dose and ways incubation was not significantly different to the pH of the soil, but the Al-dd significantly. The effect was giving the combination of Na-humate and P-fertilizer significantly, but the effect of incubation method showed no difference significant to the value of soil pH H₂O.

From Table 1 it could be shows that addition of Na-humate combination with P-fertilizer at doses of 800 ppm + 100% R had a pH value that is not significantly different from the dose of 800 ppm + 75% R, but when compared with a dose of 400 ppm + 100% R and 400 ppm + 75% R increased soil pH by 0.16 and 0.05 units respectively in the third incubation method. When compared with the controls and the way farmers, soil pH values that were subjected to a combination of Na-humate and P-fertilizer in different ways incubation also higher and to Al-dd was lower for all treatment combinations. This is consistent with experimental greenhouse Herviyanti *et. al.* (2009), where giving of 800 ppm humic materials unproductive coal combined with P-fertilizer doses of 75 and 100% R on Ultisol from Tanjung Pati Villlage, Lima Puluh Kota Regency, could increase soil pH from 5.87 to 6.28 and 6.29 units.

In Table 1 also shows that Na-humate combination with P-fertilizer in some doses gave the same effect to Al-dd soil at incubation I₁ and I₂, but the treatment of I₃, combination Na-humate and P-fertilizer dose of 800 ppm + 100 % R shows the lowest Al-dd, where there was decrease of 0.46 and 0.49 me/100 g compared to 400 ppm + 100% R and 400 ppm + 75% R, but not significantly different from 800 ppm + 75% R .

The increased in pH and decreased in Al-dd soil by providing a combination of Na-humate and P-fertilizer, due to Na-humate containing organic acids (humic and fulvic acid), could react with Al to form organo-metallic complexes or chelate that Al reduced in soil solution and pH would rises. The higher amounts of Na-humate given more functional groups that Al-dd decreases. According to Stevenson (1994) and Tan (2010) Na-humate consisted humic and fulvic acid that contains both phenol and carboxyl groups. Further described by Fessenden and Fessenden (1986) phenol and carboxylate groups contained oxygen is reactive site at the metal binding.

According to Huang and Schnitzer (1997) increasing doses of humic acid also increased functional groups of humic acid, which could form complexes with carboxyl functional groups (-COOH) and phenolic (-OH) with Al³⁺ in considerable amounts. Consequently Al-exch was reduced.

Swift (1989 *in* Alimin 2005) stated that deprotonation functional groups of humic acid would

reduce the ability of forming hydrogen bonds, both between molecules and fellow molecules would increase the amount of negative charge of functional groups from humic acid, thereby increasing inter-cluster repel force the humic acid molecules. Both effects would cause the surface of colloidal particles to be negatively charged and become more open and linear shaped on increasing soil pH.

The increased of pH also influenced by P-fertilizer that was added, because it contains elements

of P-fertilizers and also dissolved Ca. This was instrumental in raising the soil pH. While the decline in the most Al-dd was also in the mixing of Na-humate and P-fertilizer for 1 week, then incubation to soil for 1 week (I_3) treatment. Presumably this is due at the time Na-humate and P-fertilizer were first mixed, Ca from P-fertilizers in more soluble and improve soil pH. Rich (2003 in Rich, 2009) stated that the higher the P-fertilizer would increased soluble of Ca^{2+} in P-fertilizers and replace the H^+ , Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+} ions.

Table 1: Effect of Na-humate from *subbituminous* combination with P-fertilizer and ways incubation to soil pH H_2O and Al-exch.

Incubation method	Combination of Na-humate (ppm) + P-fertilizer (% R)				Average
	(400+100)	400+75)	(800+100)	(800 +75)	
Soil pH H_2O					
I_1	4.83	5.06	4.93	4.99	4.94 a
I_2	4.73	4.79	5.01	4.83	4.84 a
I_3	4.90	4.97	4.93	5.04	4.94 a
Rata-rata	4.80 B	4.91 AB	4.96 A	4.95 A	
Al-exch. (me/100 g)					
I_1	0.57 b A	0.55 b A	0.73 b A	0.72 b A	
I_2	1.52 a A	1.42 a A	1.51 a A	1.50 a A	
I_3	0.87 ab A	0.90 ab A	0.41 b B	0.53 b B	
	Control	pH = 4.60	Al-dd = 2.18		
	Farmer ways	pH = 4.68	Al-dd = 1.64		

The numbers in the same row followed by the same capital and in the same column followed by the same small letters are not significantly different according to HSD test at 5 % significance level

Note : I_1 = Na-humate incubated to the soil for 1 week and then added P-fertilizer and incubated again for 1 week.

I_2 = Na-humate and P-fertilizer applied to the soil at the same time and incubated for 2 weeks

I_3 = Na-humate and P-fertilizer were mixed for 1 week then incubated to the soil for 1 week

The content of P-available

Just giving a combination of Na-humate and P fertilizer at several doses significantly affect soil P available at third incubation method as shown in Table 2. The content P-available on the treatment dose of 800 ppm Na-Humate + 100% P-fertilizers no significance difference with a 800 ppm + 75% R. However, when compared with a dose of 400 ppm + 100% R and 400 ppm + 75% R, P-available increased by 4.14 and 5.61 ppm respectively. In line with this, Herviyanti *et al.* (2009) reported that the greenhouse experiment, giving humic material extracted from coal unproductive dose of 400 and 800 ppm to increase P-available from low to moderate criteria, respectively of 14.57 and 15.80 ppm to 20.99 ppm and 22.22 when followed with P-fertilizer 75% R, and 21.73 and 27.65 ppm when

followed by P-fertilizer 100% R. When compared with control and farmers ways showed that overall treatment combination of Na-humate and P-fertilizers in various ways incubation were given a positive response and increased P-available approximately 6.48 - 19.6 ppm.

Effect of Na-humate on the availability of P could directly through the mineralization process or indirectly by helping the release of P were fixed. According to Tan (2010), humic and fulvic acid could increase the release and solubility of P-inorganic through chelation. Aisyah (1982 in Andayani and Hayat, 2005) stated that organic acids such as humic, citric, oxalic, tartaric, malic and malonic acid to form complex compounds with hydroxy Al and Fe-Silicate poorly soluble and free phosphate ions into solution, so increasing the P-available and P- total.

Table 2: Effect of Na-humate from *subbituminous* and P-fertilizer in various ways incubation on the soil P-availability

Incubation Method	Combinations Na-humate (ppm) + P fertilizer (% recommendation)				Average
	(400+100)	400+75)	(800+100)	(800 +75)	
 ppm.....				
I ₁	14.52	15.56	22.28	15.86	17.05 a
I ₂	16.86	13.19	20.36	22.70	18.28 a
I ₃	15.78	13.99	23.14	21.01	18.48 a
Average	15.72 BC	14.25 C	21.93 A	19.86 AB	
	Control = 6.71				
	Farmer ways = 9.19				

The numbers in the same row followed by the same capital and in the same column followed by the same small letters are not significantly different according to HSD test at 5 % significance level

Note : I₁ = Na-humate incubated to the soil for 1 week and then added P-fertilizer and incubated again for 1 week.

I₂ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer applied to the soil at the same time and incubated for 2 weeks

I₃ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer were mixed for 1 week then incubated to the soil for 1 week

Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) value

Results of analysis of variance showed that there was no significant interaction with the use of a combination of Na-humate and P fertilizer at various doses in various ways incubation to the soil CEC values. Independently both Na-humate combination and fertilizer P treatment and ways incubation showed significant effect on soil CEC values as presented in Table 3. Increasing doses of Na-humate and P fertilizer will also increase soil CEC. This is because the use of Na-humate would cause the number of functional groups such as carboxyl-COOH and phenolic-OH will increase, so that the source of negative charge will increase anyway. This is supported by a statement from Soegiman (1982), the decomposition of organic material will produce organic acids that can increase the negative charge through

the dissociation of H⁺ ions from the carboxyl (-COOH) and phenolic (-OH) group. Accordingly Buffle (1984) and Stevenson (1994) suggested that the CEC of humic acid ranged from 62 -279 me/100 g, so that the use of humic acid can increase soil CEC.

Increased soil CEC due to the use of P fertilizer could be expected to occur because of the substitution of Al by Ca contained in P-fertilizer, thus precipitate Al in the form of Al (OH)₃. While increasing in soil pH caused by the deposition of Al and Fe with P to form Al (OH) H₂O, FePO₄.2H₂O and therefore increase soil pH. This is in accordance with the opinion of Hakim *et al.* (1986) that the factors effect to amount of soil CEC are soil pH, organic matter, and fertilizer. With the increase in the pH of the soil will also increase soil CEC, as well as the high content of organic matter of the soil the higher the CEC.

Table 3: Effect of Na-humate from subbituminous and P-fertilizer in various ways incubation on soil CEC

Incubation Method	Combinations Na-humate (ppm) + P fertilizer (% recommendation)				Average
	(400+100)	400+75)	(800+100)	(800 +75)	
me/100 g.....				
I ₁	14.51	13.31	20.21	17.02	16.27 a
I ₂	12.61	13.46	15.96	15.20	14.31 b
I ₃	13.45	13.43	21.03	16.11	16.01a
Average	13.53 C	13.40 C	19.01 A	16.11 B	
	Control = 9.2				
	Farmer ways = 10.69				

The numbers in the same row followed by the same capital and in the same column followed by the same small letters are not significantly different according to HSD test at 5 % significance level.

Note : I₁ = Na-humate incubated to the soil for 1 week and then added P-fertilizer and incubated again for 1 week.

I₂ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer applied to the soil at the same time and incubated for 2 weeks

I₃ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer were mixed for 1 week then incubated to the soil for 1 week

The content of organic C and N-total

The content of organic-C and total-N of Sarilamak Ultisol, Lima Puluh Kota Regency due to the use of Na-humate and fertilizer P were incubated with various ways can be presented in Table 4. There was no interaction effect between the use of Na-humate and fertilizer P and the various ways incubation on the content of soil organic-C and total-N. While the independent effect of the combination of Na-humate and fertilizer P and the incubation period is significantly to the soil organic-C, but not significant effect on soil total-N content. Ways of incubation (I₃) that provided organic-C content of 0.29% is greater than I₁ and gives 0.31% organic-C levels higher than I₂ incubation method.

In Table 4 shows that the highest organic C values actually obtained on the use of a combination of Na-humate dose of 800 ppm + 75% R of P-fertilizer, although not significantly different from the dose of 800 ppm +100% R, but could increase soil organic-C 0.52 % and as much as 0.53% higher than the 400 ppm + 100% R and 400 ppm + 75% R. This is due to Na-humate given have a high content of organic-C is equal to 42.26%, the increase in Na-humate dose will also increase soil organic-C content. While the content

of total-N soil did not change significantly with the provision of Na-humate and fertilizer P due to the low N content of Na-humate is added (3.2%). According to Umar (2002 in Mansyur 2003) differences in soil organic matter content is as a result of differences in the dose of organic matter was given. Further stated that the addition of organic matter with a high dose will deliver a high organic-C anyway, so raise the levels of soil organic matter. Huang and Schnitzer (1997) stated that humic acid as a component of the humic compounds contained elements of C=56.2%, O₂=35.5%, N=3.2%, H=4.7%, S=0.8% and fulvic acid contains elements of C=45.7%, O₂=44.8%, N=2.1%, H=5.4%, S=1.9%. Humic fractions in the form of humic acid are usually rich in carbon which ranges between 41 and 57% (Tan, 2010).

Based on the results of chemical analysis of soil that has been previously submitted can be stated that the addition of Na-humate and fertilizer P in a variety of ways incubation to improve the chemical properties with increasing soil pH, organic C, KTK and nutrient elements such as P available, instead of Al-dd dropped. Especially when compared with the control and the way farmers, in general, the study is able to improve the fertility of the land that will be planted with rice.

Table 4: Effect of Na-humate subbituminous and P-fertilizer in various ways incubation on organic C and soil N- total.

Incubation Method	Combinations Na-humate (ppm) + P fertilizer (% recommendation))				Average
	(400+100)	(400+75)	(800+100)	(800 +75)	
C-organic (%)					
I ₁	2.09	2.38	2.51	2.88	2.46 b
I ₂	2.33	2.08	2.59	2.78	2.44 b
I ₃	2.67	2.66	2.84	2.86	2.75 a
Average	2.36 B	2.37 B	2.65 AB	2.84 A	
N-total (%)					
I ₁	0.23	0.21	0.21	0.24	0.22 a
I ₂	0.23	0.25	0.27	0.21	0.24 a
I ₃	0.22	0.23	0.20	0.26	0.22 a
Average	0.23 A	0.23 A	0.22 A	0.24 A	
Control : C-organic = 2.02 and N-total = 0.098					
Farmer ways : C organic = 2.35 and N total = 0.17					

The numbers in the same row followed by the same capital and in the same column followed by the same small letters are not significantly different according to HSD test at 5 % significance level

Note : I₁ = Na-humate incubated to the soil for 1 week and then added P-fertilizer and incubated again for 1 week.

I₂ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer applied to the soil at the same time and incubated for 2 weeks

I₃ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer were mixed for 1 week then incubated to the soil for 1 week

Component Crop observation

The content of Al and P from Upland Rice

The Al content analysis of roots and the top (stem + leaves) from upland rice of the sample taken on plant at the time of maximum vegetative growth (76 DAP), are presented in Table 5. Interactions of Na-humate and P-fertilizer were incubated with various ways can give no significant effect on the content of Al crops while the main influence from the combination of Na-humate and fertilizer P have significant effect. It shows that for the Al content of roots upland rice with the use of Na-humate and P fertilizer (800 ppm +100% R) could suppress Al crop levels and as such the most effective number of 0.013 and 0.018 % compared to the doses of 400 ppm + 100% R and 400 ppm + 75% R but not significantly different from the treatment of 800 ppm Na-humate + 75% R P-fertilizer. While incubation ways I₃ and I₁ have Al roots content lower than I₂. This is due to the use of 800 ppm Na-humate +

100% R P-fertilizer and incubation ways I₃ and I₁ could reduce soil Al-dd is also higher (Table 1), so that Al uptake by the plant would be less.

The top content of Al upland rice at treatment 800 ppm Na-humate + 100% R of fertilizer P was the lowest. Value (%) lower by 0.013 than the use of 400 ppm + 75% R, although not significantly different from other treatments. In general, when compared with the control and the way farmers, the Al content in the roots and the top of upland rice showed lower values for all treatments of a combination of Na-humate and P-fertilizer in a variety of ways incubation.

From Table 5 shows that for all treatments of a combination of Na-humate and P-fertilizer at various doses and with multiple ways incubation, the roots of Al content higher than the top of upland rice. This means that there was accumulation of Al in the roots and only ± 50% of that in the translocation to the upper plant. In other words, upland rice varieties Inpago 6 has the ability to inhibit the movement of Al from the roots to the top, so that plant growth is not disturbed.

Table 5: Effects of Na-humate and P-fertilizer by various incubation on the content of Al from the roots and the top of the crop

Incubation Method	Combinations Na-humate (ppm) + P fertilizer (% recommendation)				Average
	(400+100)	(400+75)	(800+100)	(800 +75)	
Roots (%)					
I ₁	0.102	0.092	0.071	0.077	0.086 a
I ₂	0.087	0.099	0.082	0.086	0.089 a
I ₃	0.078	0.092	0.075	0.079	0.081 a
Average	0.089 AB	0.094 A	0.076 C	0.081 BC	
Stem + leaf (%)					
	0.057	0.066	0.046	0.051	0.056 a
I ₂	0.048	0.052	0.043	0.043	0.047 a
I ₃	0.054	0.054	0.042	0.047	0.049 a
Average	0.053 AB	0.057 A	0.044 B	0.047 AB	
Control	Al roots =	0.122	Al Stem + leaf =	0,095	
Farmer ways	Al -roots =	0,099	Al Stem + leaf =	0.092	

The numbers in the same row followed by the same capital and in the same column followed by the same small letters are not significantly different according to HSD test at 5 % significance level

Note : I₁ = Na-humate incubated to the soil for 1 week and then added P-fertilizer and incubated again for 1 week.

I₂ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer applied to the soil at the same time and incubated for 2 weeks

I₃ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer were mixed for 1 week then incubated to the soil for 1 week

Content of P plant

The results of the statistical analysis of observations of plant P content are presented in Table 6. The interaction effect of the use of Na-humate and P-fertilizer were incubated with various ways and major influence of the combination of Na-humate and fertilizer P did not show significant effect on P-content upland rice. Meanwhile, incubation method has significant effect on the top of the plant P content.

Furthermore, in Table 5 shows that the use of Na-humate with P-fertilizer blended especially for 1

week and then incubated to the land for a week (I₃) could increase content of P the top of the plant each at 0.060 and 0.067% when compared with the incubation I₁ and I₂. This is due to P fertilizer mixed with Na-humate for 1 week becomes more soluble, and when applied to the soil more quickly available, so it can be absorbed by plants in greater numbers. Observations plant P content were obtained for all treatments as well as the increase in available P (Table 2) in the soil.

Table 6: Effect of Na-humate and P-fertilizers in various ways incubation on content of P roots and tops of upland rice.

Incubation Method	Combinations Na-humate (ppm) + P fertilizer (% recommendation)				Average
	(400+100)	(400+75)	(800+100)	(800 +75)	
Roots (%)					
I ₁	0.223	0.182	0.257	0.237	0.225a
I ₂	0.197	0.177	0.247	0.217	0.209 a
I ₃	0.193	0.170	0.230	0.190	0.196 a
Average	0.204 A	0.176 A	0.244 A	0.214 A	
Stem + leaf					
I ₁	0.230	0.263	0.293	0.270	0.264 b
I ₂	0.270	0.230	0.277	0.250	0.257 b
I ₃	0.310	0.277	0.367	0.343	0.324 a
Average	0.270 A	0.257 A	0.312 A	0.288 A	
Control	P roots = 0.083		P Stem + leaf = 0.213		
Farmer ways	P roots = 0.163		P Stem + leaf = 0.265		

The numbers in the same row followed by the same capital and in the same column followed by the same small letters are not significantly different according to HSD test at 5 % significance level

Note : I₁ = Na-humate incubated to the soil for 1 week and then added P-fertilizer and incubated again for 1 week.

I₂ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer applied to the soil at the same time and incubated for 2 weeks

I₃ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer were mixed for 1 week then incubated to the soil for 1 week

Plant Production Component

Milled rice (MR) or seed dry weight (Water content = 14%)

Results of analysis of variance showed that there was a significant interaction effect between the use of combination Na-humate and fertilizer P with three ways incubations on dry weight of seed in 14% water content as shown in Table 7. The use of Na-humate 800 ppm and fertilizer P 100 and 75% R have higher dry weight than the use of Na-humate 400 ppm and the amount of P fertilizer the same level for all three incubation methods. The results of the highest grain dry weight obtained with the use of Na-humate 800 ppm + 100 R of fertilizer P by incubation I₃, where this treatment could improve the outcome of milled rice from 1.38 to 3.78 Mg/ha compared to other treatments. These results are almost as good as the treatment of 800 ppm + 75% on the same incubation manner. The results obtained are above the average production of upland rice varieties Inpago 6 (3.9 Mg/ha) and approaching potential outcomes that can be achieved is 5.81 Mg/ha (description of the Rice Research Institute, 2010). So also with the use of Na-humate 400 ppm, both combined with 100% and 75% R of fertilizer P showed almost the same results by incubation I₁ and I₃. This suggests that the use of Na-humate incubated with P fertilizer into the soil before it is given or mixed first P fertilizers can save up to 25% recommendation.

The results obtained are consistent with the improvement of soil chemical properties after incubated with Na-humate and P fertilizer at various doses and incubation method. Levels of soil Al-exch (Table 1) is lower, available P (Table 2), and CEC soil (Table 3) were higher in treatment I₃ no longer leads to the presence of heavy metals, especially Al toxicity to plants, and the roots could grow properly. Good development of root was provided, opportunities nutrient uptake, especially P (Table 6) for more, which improves plant growth and ultimately provide high yields.

Furthermore, when considered Table 7 it could be stated that the use of Na-humate and P fertilizer mixed manner for 1 week prior to the new land were incubated for 1 week (I₃) obtained results significantly higher respectively at 1.16 and 1.61 Mg/ha compared to I₁ and I₂ at various doses of Na-humate and fertilizer P. This means that by incubation I₃ could give nutrient solubility of P was higher (Table 2), followed by a high P uptake as well (Table 5), so that the results obtained reaching a value of 5.58 Mg/ha.

When compared with the controls and the way farmers, the use a combination of Na-humate and fertilizer P at different dose and how incubation could increase crop yield of upland rice are very real from 2.84 and 3.25 to 5.58 Mg/ha, meaning an increase of 96.48% compared to control and 71.69% compared to the way farmers. This suggests that farmer's fertilizer P was given as 100% R to the soil, is very little that could absorbed by plant roots because without Na-humate, P-fertilizer will be bound in the soil.

Table 7. Effect of combination Na-humate and P-fertilizers in various ways incubation for milled rice

Incubation method	Combinations Na-humate (ppm) + P fertilizer (% recommendation)				Average
	(400+100)	400+75)	(800+100)	(800 +75)	
	Milled rice (t ha ⁻¹)				
I ₁	3.96 b B	3.87 ab B	5.29 a A	5.09 a A	
I ₂	3.82 b B	3.14 b C	4.52 b A	4.34 b AB	
I ₃	4.67 a B	4.68 a B	5.58 a A	4.76 ab AB	
Control	= 2.84				Farmer ways = 3.25

The numbers in the same row followed by the same capital and in the same column followed by the same small letters are not significantly different according to HSD test at 5 % significance level

Note : I₁ = Na-humate incubated to the soil for 1 week and then added P-fertilizer and incubated again for 1 week.

I₂ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer applied to the soil at the same time and incubated for 2 weeks

I₃ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer were mixed for 1 week then incubated to the soil for 1 week

Dry Weight of 1000 seeds (g)

Effect of interactions from Na-humate and fertilizer P were incubated with various ways and major influence of the manner of incubation give no significant effect on the weight of 1000 grains of upland rice. While the main effect a combination of dose Na- of humate and P fertilizer affect significantly on dry weight of 1000 seeds as presented in Table 8.

The use of Na-humate and P fertilizer on dose 400 ppm + 100% R, 800 ppm + 100% R and 800 ppm and 75% R on the third incubation method showed that seed quality is almost the same, but all three treatments that have quality seed were better than the use of 400 ppm Na humate and P-fertilizer 75% R.

Weight of 1000 seeds in all three treatments were higher by about 1.43 - 1.82 g. This is due to the content of P-available soil treatment 400 ppm + 75% R will be lower in the three other treatments (Table 2) and P content of the plant will also be low (Table 6). As explained previously that the greater availability of P would provide better root growth and seed production would increase. In other words, the higher P uptake would increase upland rice grain filling so as to provide better quality seeds. According Setiamidjaja (1986), a high P uptake would triggered root growth and establishment of a good root system of young plants, thus accelerating flowering, ripening of fruits and seeds, and increases seed production as well as the building blocks of the cell nucleus, fat and protein.

Table 8. Effect of combination Na-humate and P fertilizer P in various ways incubation on 1000 grain weight

Incubation method	Combinations Na-humate (ppm) + P fertilizer (% recommendation)				Average
	(400+100)	(400+75)	(800+100)	(800 +75)	
	Dry weight 1000 seeds (g)				
I ₁	22.30	21.05	23.06	22.57	22.25 a
I ₂	21.13	20.67	22.57	22.53	21.97 a
I ₃	22.43	20.90	23.48	22.26	22.27 a
Average	21.95 AB	20.87 B	23.03 A	22.46 A	

Rice : Control = 19.55 farmer ways = 20.56

The numbers in the same row followed by the same capital and in the same column followed by the same small letters are not significantly different according to HSD test at 5 % significance level

Note : I₁ = Na-humate incubated to the soil for 1 week and then added P-fertilizer and incubated again for 1 week.

I₂ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer applied to the soil at the same time and incubated for 2 weeks

I₃ = Na-humate and P-fertilizer were mixed for 1 week then incubated to the soil for 1 week

CONCLUSION

1. In general it can be stated that the use of Na-humate combination of *subbituminous* and fertilizer P at various doses and incubation ways to reduce the toxicity of metal Al, thus providing growth relatively better upland rice and grain yield were relatively higher in rural Sarilamak Ultisol, Sub Harau, Lima Puluh Kota District, West Sumatra, Indonesia. However, the yield of rice in various ways incubation by mixing Na-humate and fertilizer P for 1 week, then new to the land incubated for 1 week (I_3) has a slightly higher yield than incubation way of Na-humate to the soil for 1 week followed by incubation fertilizer P for 1 week (I_1) and the use of Na-humate and P fertilizers simultaneously, then incubated for 2 weeks (I_2).
2. Best treatment interaction and optimal rice yield is the use of 800 ppm Na-humate and 100% R P-fertilizer in a way I_3 incubation that is equal to 5.58 Mg/ha. However, this result is almost the same as the the use of 800 ppm Na-humate + 75% R P-fertilizer with incubation I_3 way too. This suggests that application of Na-humate fertilizer P can save up to 25%.

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